

doi:10.5281/zenodo.19800867

Analysis Of Concord Errors In Written English Of Selected Students From Five Tertiary Institutions In Yobe State

***Abdulwahab Yerima & Babagana Modu**

Umar Suleiman College of Education, Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria

***Corresponding Author: abdulwahabyerima@yahoo.com**

ABSTRACT

The research analyzed Concord Errors in Written English of Selected Students from Five Tertiary Institutions in Yobe State. All Diploma and NCE students from State Polytechnic, Geidam, Federal College of Education (Technical), Potiskum, College of Agriculture, Gujba, Umar Suleiman College of Education, Gashua and College of Education and Legal Studies, Nguru constitute the population of the study. Out of the total population of 500 students, 100 from each school were used as sample of the study to represent the whole. Structured tests as instruments for data collection (comprehension and discourse writing) were administered for investigation. The data gathered were analyzed in a tabular form using frequency and percentage of occurrence. The study looked at the areas of applicability of the rules of concord and their exceptions in written English. Areas of concord the research covered include subject/verb, subject-object agreement, pronoun-antecedent agreement, and tense agreement commonly used in students' daily communication. The choice of the topic arose from the experiences of the researchers as teachers of English and the importance of English as a medium of instruction in Nigerian education system. In addition, NCE and Diploma were deliberately chosen for the study with the aim of finding out students' performance concerning grammatical concord in the use of English.

Keywords: Concord, Error, Error Analysis, Written English.

INTRODUCTION

Concord, universally, means agreement between constituents' elements of a sentence (Aarts, 2021). For a sentence to be properly constructed there must be an agreement of its components. The elements of the sentence, which are interrelated, include Subject-Verb (SV), Subject-Verb-Object (SVO), Subject-Verb-Complement (SVC), Subject-Verb-Adjunct (SVA), Subject-Verb-Complement-Adjunct (SVCA), etc. The Subject, which usually performs the action, often occurs as a nominal phrase and what comes after it, a verbal phrase, expresses the action, so that the two elements constitute the subject-verb structure (SV); the remaining constituents perform different functions in a sentence. Concord in English grammar ensures consistency and harmony between different elements of a sentence. It is the relationship whereby certain words within a sentence must correspond in number, person, gender, or case to achieve grammatical correctness and clarity (Jafar, 2016 & Hewings, 2023). Relatedly, concord is the formal agreement between the subject and the verb, or between other related grammatical elements, to produce structurally correct sentences (Nurially, 2022). Correct use of concord enhances grammatical accuracy, clarity, and effective communication in English. Failure to observe concord often results in errors, especially in written English, which can obscure meaning and reduce communicative competence (Sharhazad, 2021).

Working from the 'Error Analysis' (EA) point of view, Scheider and McCoy (2002) and Hussain (2019), found the written English of undergraduates to be characterized by ambiguous sentences and paragraphs, incorrect spellings, and incorrect use of grammatical concord. The present study differs from the previous

studies mentioned here in that it goes beyond describing the situation; it examines the implications of the situation on the academic performance of the students with a view to alleviating the problem.

Statement of the Problem

In higher institutions, many students can hardly construct sentences that are free from concord errors (Ellis, 2015). The errors tend to manifest in their written English. This troubling situation is a source of great concern. Many researchers like Ellis (2015), Yang (2019) and Leila (2021) have conducted studies on the performance of students in various aspects of grammar, yet, the problem persists. More worrisome is that the researchers, in the course of their daily interactions with students at all levels and programs – NCE and Diploma, notice concord errors. This issue is very disturbing, given that the English language is the springboard from which all other subjects can be learned. It is the official language of instruction in Nigerian tertiary institutions and if students fail to grasp its rudiments such as concord, then one would be right to conclude that the entire educational system is in jeopardy because teaching and learning are done in English. Thus, there is a motivation to study the phenomenon with a view to further highlighting it and contributing useful suggestions aimed at reducing the numerous concord errors committed by English language users.

Objectives of the Study

The research objectives were to:

1. investigate the extent to which students use concord in their written English;
2. identify which classes of concord errors students mostly commit in tertiary institutions; and
3. examine the implications of concord errors on the written English of students in tertiary institutions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Concord

Hewings (2023) described concord as the morphosyntactic phenomenon whereby one element (e.g. verb, adjective, or determiner) takes a form that matches certain grammatical features. Such features include person, number, gender, case, and definiteness. Bakurro (2015) and Jafar (2016) asserted that the correct application of grammatical concord rules provides the language user with the means to construct good English. Thus, for communication, especially, written communication to be effective in English language, there should be harmony among the words in a sentence. To buttress this view, Uchegba Ekuorume and Okongor (2015) opined that for a sentence to be grammatically correct all its elements must be in harmony with one another. The misapplication of the rules of concord may, therefore, affect flawless communication and lead to misunderstanding by the reader,. Since there is an undeniable connection between the structure of an utterance and its comprehensibility, non-native students should, thus, strive to learn how to make effective use of the rules of concord in English for their written communication to be effective and correct.

A) The violation of rule of subject-verb agreement informs the following sentence errors:

1. She **cry** bitterly.
2. The woman **have** two children.
3. He **do not** understand the lesson.

The correct sentences for the above errors are:

1. She **cries** bitterly.
2. The woman **has** two children.
3. He **does not** understand the lesson.

B) The wrong choices of pronoun/ antecedent by some speakers of English create errors in the use of sentences as follows:

1. Everyone ate their food.

2. Has anyone brought their camera?

3. Each of the student wanted to submit their assignment

The correct pronoun/ antecedent concord should read:

1. Everyone ate his food.

2. Has anyone brought his camera?

3. Each of the students wanted to submit his assignment

C) The misuse of subject/object agreement leads to errors in sentences as follows:

1. He injured herself on the hand.

2. She is making sweater for himself.

3. I will sing yourself.

The corrected forms should read:

1. He injured himself on the hand.

2. She is making sweater for herself.

↓
3rd Per Sg

↓
Refl. Pron Fem.

3. I will sing myself.

↓
1st Per Sg

↓
Refl. Pron. Pl.

D) The consistency in the use of tenses leads to the following errors:

1. We heard that the provost travels monthly.
2. I learned from the Geography class that the world was spherical.

The consistent sentences of the above are:

1. We hear that the provost travels monthly.
2. I learned from the Geography class that the world is spherical.

Error as a Concept

Ellis (2015) and Yang (2019) saw error as a language deviation from precision or correctness. They distinguish between errors and mistakes since Lionny (2022) associated the former with a lack of knowledge. Though, Ellis (2015) argued that students make a mistake if they occasionally provide the correct form and occasionally apply the erroneous one, mistakes stem from the learner's ability to apply what they have learned. However, it indicates an error if students consistently employ the erroneous form. This definition indicates that 'mistake' is a fault that a learner can correct, while 'error' is a fault that learner cannot correct (Nuruzzaman, 2018; Yang, 2019).

Error Analysis

Ellis (2015) and James (2018) posited error analysis as the study of learners' errors in order to understand how they acquire a second language, identify difficulties, and develop teaching strategies. Unlike simple mistake correction, it systematically investigates errors to uncover the learners' interlanguage system. Mufti (2023) described error analysis as research aids in identifying the underlying factors and sources of these anticipated errors made through the process of second language learning. This, as he points out, enhances our comprehension of language learning and also supports the implementation of appropriate teaching techniques and approaches to increase students' appreciation of the value of learning a foreign language effectively and successfully.

Written English

Nurially (2022) and Sharhzad (2021) portrayed written English as the representation of the English in written form, following grammatical, lexical, and stylistic conventions that differ from spoken English. It emphasizes accuracy, clarity, organization, and standardization

Hussain (2019) and Leila (2021) identified challenges in learning written English as grammar and concord, vocabulary choice, spelling mechanics, coherence and cohesion among others

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

The study areas covered State Polytechnic Geidam, Federal College of Education (Technical) Potiskum, College of Agriculture Damaturu, Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua, and College of Education and Legal Studies Nguru.

A total of five hundred (500) students were drawn through simple random sampling and used for the study. The researchers believed that this number provides adequate data for the present study.

Method of Data Collection

A test instrument was used for data collection. The test consisted of five exercises. Exercise ‘A’ which is on subject/verb agreement deals with an alternative choice of twenty questions for the responders to select one out of two words in brackets that best suit the given sentences. Exercise ‘B’ contains a test of subject/object has twenty questions responders choose one out of two words that fit into the context of the sentences. Exercise ‘C’ deals with pronoun/antecedent and contains twenty questions with two alternative words in parentheses for the students to decide the correct answers and Exercise ‘D’ is a test on tense agreement in which respondents will choose the best answer from two words in brackets in the given sentences. The second phase consisted of Exercise ‘E’ which tests students’ performance on written discourse on ‘How to Make a Pot in My Locality’ in one paragraph.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers sought the consent of the participants and the school management, especially to request their time, energy and their willingness to participate in organizing the classes for the testing, marking and scoring of the students. It is going to be a very tedious task, which for the researchers’ formal request alone cannot be granted, but in order to obtain data for the research, their time and cooperation again were requested once again to participate in the test. It was also observed that having the sessions with the students during school hours would distraction other classes also in session. To deal with that, the researchers and research assistants sought permission to hold the classes after school closing hours.

DATA ANALYSIS

The test scripts of the participants were collected and analysed using simple frequency percentages. There were 80 alternative questions on the test item marked out of eighty, and the other 20 marks were given to a test on composition, totalling 100 marks. The grammatical concord forms in the tests - comprehension and composition - were identified based on the four types of concord - subject/verb, subject/object, pronoun/antecedent, and tense agreement, and analyses would follow in order to determine whether the students have used them correctly or incorrectly.

The expected results obtained were tabulated from Category A to Category D under Subject/ verb Agreement, Subject/object Agreement, Pronoun/Antecedent Agreement, and Tense Agreement as shown below:

State Polytechnic, Geidam

Average Score Category by Category

Category A Subject/verb Agreement	Category B Subject/Object Agreement	Category C Pronoun/Antecedent Agreement	Category D Tense Agreement
45.35%	60%	63%	30%

The respondents scored less than the average mark in subject/verb agreement with (40.35%). The subject/object agreement indicates that the majority of the students passed with (60%), as well as in pronoun/antecedent agreement with (63%), which is also a good performance. However, in tense agreement the respondents scored (30%), which is less than the average marks in the use of English.

Federal College of Education (Technical), Potiskum

Average Score Category by Category

Category A Subject/Verb Agreement	Category B Subject/Object Agreement	Category C Pronoun/Antecedent Agreement	Category D Tense Agreement
45.35%	62%	73%	39%

The respondents scored nearly the average mark and slightly beyond it in subject/ verb agreement with (45.35%). Subject/object agreement at (62%) indicates majority of them passed with percentages above average marks, while in pronoun/antecedent agreement, the score was an excellent at (73%). However, in tense agreement, the respondents scored (39%), which is below the average marks in the use of concord in their written English.

College of Agriculture, Gujba

Average Score Category by Category

Category A Subject/Verb Agreement	Category B Subject/Object Agreement	Category C Pronoun/Antecedent Agreement	Category D Tense Agreement
40.35%	50%	63%	25%

The respondents scored less than average marks in subject/verb agreement (40.35%), with subject/object agreement (50%) showing that the majority passed with average marks. The pronoun/antecedent agreement score was very good at (63%), but in tense agreement, the respondents scored (25%), which is below the average marks for concord usage in students' English.

Umar Suleiman College of Education, Gashua

Average Score Category by Category

Category A Subject/Verb Agreement	Category B Subject/Object Agreement	Category C Pronoun/Antecedent Agreement	Category D Tense Agreement
50%	60.5%	70.5%	38%

The respondents performed averagely in subject/verb agreement with (50%), and in subject/object agreement with an appreciable score of (60.5%). In pronoun/antecedent agreement, the students performed better than the other types of concord with (70.5%), however, in tense agreement, the score was (38%), which is rated below the average score.

College of Legal and Islamic Studies Nguru

Average Score Category by Category

Category A Subject/Verb Agreement	Category B Subject/Object Agreement	Category C Pronoun/Antecedent Agreement	Category D Tense Agreement
45.35%	55%	73%	40%

The respondents scored below average in subject/verb agreement at (45.35%), and in subject/object agreement at (55%), indicating that a majority passed with average marks. They scored (73%) in pronoun/antecedent agreement, which is categorized as excellent performance, however, in the use tense agreement, the respondents scored less than the average marks with (40%) in the concord use in English.

DISCUSSION

This study identified and analysed concord errors in written English of Diploma, NCE and undergraduate students from State Polytechnic Geidam, Federal College of Education (Technical) Potiskum, College of Agriculture Gujba, Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua, and College of Education and Legal Studies Nguru. The frequencies of concord errors in the written English of selected students are:

The study found out that students in tertiary institutions, to a large extent commit concord errors in their written discourse in English. In all the 100 comprehension and composition (80 and 20, respectively) tests administered to the sampled students, various types of concord errors were found.

The study revealed that the students mostly commit concord errors in the use of subject/verb and tenses. Respondents from the five institutions (State Polytechnic Geidam, Federal College of Education (Technical) Potiskum, College of Agriculture Gujba, Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua, and College of Education and Legal Studies Nguru) do not handle subject/verb and tense agreement very well as revealed in their test' results. The data collected from the five tertiary institutions under the study, reveal tense concord to be the major problem area for the students. The students misuse of present and past tenses, and present perfective with past perfect, along with the wrong choice of adverbials to the main verb in a sentence. This supports claim by Bakurro (2015) and Jafar (2016) that the written English of undergraduates is characterized by ambiguous sentences and paragraphs, wrong spellings, and incorrect use of concord. This also justifies the position of Ellis (2015) and Yang (2019), who say most the students in tertiary institutions fall short in their application of the rules of in the use of English. Students, they argue (Bakurro, and Jafar), are left at a crossroads when faced with exceptions to some fundamental rules governing concord.

Lionny (2022) also corroborated this assertion by stating that many learners of English as a second language confuse themselves with the grammatical rules that pertain to their mother tongue. Rules of the mother tongue (L1) often contradict those of their second language (L2), thus leading learners to commit concord errors unconsciously.

The study proved that concord errors committed by the students of the five institutions under consideration have serious implications for their academic performance. It is evident from their test scripts that the more they commit concord errors in the use of English the poorer their performance. This problem results in mass failure of students in all the courses they undertake since all their courses are taught in English. The students' discourses are completely unreadable. This is because they are incomprehensible as they contain many concord errors and other errors such as spelling mistakes, mixed-ups or muddled thoughts. Their paragraphs do not contain dominant ideas or apparent cohesive devices, and their ideas do not flow smoothly.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it is concluded that the subject/verb and tense concord constitute the major problem areas for the subjects generally. It is also concluded that most of the students in Diploma 11 and NCE 111 students have limited knowledge of grammatical concord in the use of English. They also have limited knowledge of the rules governing grammatical concord and how and where the rules are applied in English. Concerted efforts should be made to eliminate it completely or reduce the problem to the barest minimum.

RECOMMENDATIONS

These recommendations are made to improve students' grammatical concord in written their English:

1. Constant drill practice on the part of the students should be encouraged regularly and consistently as this will improve their performance in written English at tertiary institutions.
2. Qualified, competent and professional teachers of the subject/course should be employed in order to teach efficiently at our tertiary institutions, as well as increase students' academic performance in the use of English.
3. English language related courses should not be assigned to teachers with professions other than English, as this will affect the students' performance in the use of English at tertiary institutions.
4. Teachers should emphasize and adopt interactive teaching learning techniques so that the students will learn gradually when they are engaged with a varieties of exercises and simulations.
5. Teachers should strive hard to reduce the number of errors committed by our students, if it truly means improving their performance. That is, as performance increases, errors decreases, and vice-versa.

6. Students should be encouraged to read varieties of genres (English textbooks) which will develop their writing proficiency and help them use English effectively and efficiently.
7. Curriculum developers and textbook writers should undertake a periodic review of the contents and styles of course materials. This will help them address the problem of grammatical concord in the use of English identified in the structural tests and written discourse of students at tertiary institutions.

REFERENCES

- Aarts, B., McMahon, A. M. S., & Hinrichs, L. (2021). *The Handbook of English Linguistics*. Wiley Blackwell.
- Bakurro, J. (2015). *Concord in English Grammar: Problems and Recommendations for Senior High School Student*: Munich, GRIN Verlag.
- Ellis, R. (2015). *Understanding Second Language Acquisition (2nd Ed.)*. Oxford Applied Linguistics Oxford University Press.
- Hewings, M. (2023). *Advanced Grammar in Use: Fourth Edition*: Cambridge: Cambridge University Press & Assessment. Retrieved from <http://www.cambridge.org/gb/cambridgeenglish/catalog/grammar-use-4th-edition>.
- Hussain, M. & Abdullah, R. (2019). *An Analysis of Undergraduate Saudi EFL Female Students Error in Written English Essays*. *Arab world English Journal (AWE) Special Issue: The Dynamics of EFL in Saudi Arabia*, 241-258. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssm.3512533>.
- Jafar, S. (2016). *Analysis of concord use Errors in the Written English of Diploma Students in Selected Institutions in Jigawa State*. (M.Ed thesis, ABU Zaria).
- James, C. (2018). *Errors in Language Use: Exploring Error Analysis*. England: Pearson Education Limited.
- Leila, L. & Saliha, C. (2021). *Error Analysis of English Expository Paragraphs Written by Third Year Scientific Stream Students at Badi Mekki High School, Biskra*. *Djoussour Elmaarefa*, 7(2), 753-763.
- Lionny, G.P. & Kusumadewi, H. (2022). *An Error Analysis on the Use of Simple Past Tense in Students Recount Text Writing*. *JEDU: Journal of English Education*, 2(1), 32-39. <http://doi.org/10.30888/jedu.v2i.6428>
- Muftah, M. (2023). *Data-Driven Learning (DDL) Activities: Do they Truly Promote EFL Students Writing Skills Development?* *Education and Information Technologies*, 1-27. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-11620-z>
- Ndimili, M. (2019). *Languages and Culture in Nigeria*. A Festschrift for Okon Essien, Publisher
- Nuriaily, N. (2022). *An Analysis of Error Made by English Language Education Department Students in English Paragraph Writing*. *JALL (Journal of Applied Linguistics and Literacy)*, 6(1), 93-109. <http://dx.doi.org/10.25157/jall.v6i1.6657>.
- Nuruzzaman, M. & Hamed, M. (2018). *Common Linguistic Errors among Non-native Libyan Students Writing*. *Arab World English Journal*, 9(3), 219-232. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssm.3258802>.
- Scheider, P. and McCoy, K. F. (2002). *Socio – Cultural Theory and Second Language Learning*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Sharhzad, S., Muhammad, N., Farooqi, S.M. & Raheem, Z (2021). *Effect of Teaching Graduate Course in English on Error in English Writing*. *Llkgretim Online*, 20(2), 398-406. <http://doi.org/10.17051/iikononline.2021.02.42>.
- Uchegba-Ekwueme, C. & Okongor, T.A. (2015). *Concord and Problem Associated with Nigerian Learners of English: Proceedings of the Academic Conference of African Scholar Publications and Research International on New Strategies and Approaches* 5(2), 6th august, 2015. Federal University Dutse, Students Centre Hall, Dutse, Jigawa State, Nigeria.
- Yang, X. (2019). *A Review of Negative Language Transfer Regarding the Errors in English Writing in Chinese Colleges*. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 10(3), 603-609. <http://doi.org/10.30888/jedu.v2i.6428>